

DESIGN AND ANALYSIS OF RECIPROCATING DOUBLE ACTING TWO STAGE AIR COMPRESSOR CRANKSHAFT

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ABSTRACT:

Air compressor has earned a fair amount of popularity amongst various industries due to diverse uses of compressor air in applications such as driving of air engines(air motors), operation of blast furnace, Bessemer conveyors, supercharging of I.C. engines to name a few. The air compressors are available in various capacities and types. Mainly there are two types of compressor is driven by prime mover such as diesel engines or electric motor or sometimes turbine through crankshaft. In this paper crankshaft was designed by considering torsional and bending moments. After designed model was developed in Creo. Static structural and transient analysis was carried out in ANSYS.

KEYWORDS: Compressor, crankshaft, analysis.

1. INTRODUCTION:

In order to successfully control, the noise and vibration, the vibration of reciprocating compressor crankshaft, which can cause vibration and noise of the compressor, and some even can destroy crankshaft bearing and crankshaft itself must be estimated and analysed. So early in design stage, computations of natural frequencies, mode shapes, and critical speeds of crankshaft system are indispensable. Thus, an accurate model for prediction of the vibration of a crankshaft system is essential for reciprocating compressor. Vibration of the crankshaft system is a complex three dimensional coupled vibration under running conditions, including the torsional, longitudinal and lateral vibrations.

2. DESIGN:

2.1 CRANKSHAFT DESIGN:

S_e = Allowable fatigue strength

P_r = Tangential force

Table I. Crankshaft Material Properties

Material	SG Iron 600/3
Factor of safety	1.5-2
Ultimate Tensile Strength	600Mpa.
Yield strength	370MPa

Case-I: Position of crankshaft at TDC and it is subjected to maximum bending moment and zero torsional moment.

Table II. Reaction Forces At Different Locations Of Crankshaft

Point	Description	Reaction(kg)		Moment(kg-mm)	
		Horiz	Vert	Horiz	Vert
A	Bearing1	-409.404	-386.54	0	0
B	HP Crank	0	-959.158	-45853.3	34333.08
C	LP Crank	0	2684.885	-98666.5	197608.9
D	HP Crank	0	-959.158	151479.8	14534.5
E	Bearing2	1371.09	714.02	215497.5	56769
F	Flywheel	961.6894	254	0	0

Bending moment is highest at point C. So resultant bending moment,

$$M_c = \sqrt{(M_{CH})^2 + (M_{cv})^2} = 220871.855 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Torsional moment at c is given by,

$$M_t = F_t \cdot r = 0$$

$$(M_{te}) = \sqrt{(M_c * K_b)^2 + (M_t * K_t)^2} = 3301307.782 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Diameter of shaft under shear strength,

$$\tau = \frac{\Pi}{16 * d_c^3} M_{te}$$

$$d_c = 42.071 \text{ mm}$$

Diameter of shaft under bending strength,

$$M_{be} = \frac{1}{2} [M_b * K_b + M_{te}] = 331307.782 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

$$d_c = \sqrt[3]{\frac{32 * M_{be}}{\pi * \sigma_b}} = 44.71 \text{ mm}$$

Diameter of shaft under fatigue strength,

$$d_c = \sqrt[3]{\frac{32 * M_{be}}{\pi * S_e}} = 98.187 \text{ mm}$$

Design of crankpin,

$$(M_{te}) = \sqrt{(M_b * K_b)^2 + (M_t * K_t)^2} = 79097.653 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Diameter on the basis of shear strength,

$$d_c = \frac{16}{\pi * \tau} M_{te} = 26.10 \text{ mm}$$

Diameter on the bending strength,

$$M_{be} = \frac{1}{2} [M_b * K_b + M_{te}] = 75689.9275 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

$$d_c = \sqrt[3]{\frac{32 * M_{be}}{\pi * \sigma_b}} = 27.33 \text{ mm}$$

Design of web:

Thickness of web,

$$t = 0.7d = 70 \text{ mm}$$

Width of web

$$w = 1.14d_c = 114 \text{ mm}$$

Compressive stress due to $(R_1)_v$

$$\sigma_c = \frac{R_1}{w * t} = 0.1347 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Bending stress due to $(R_1)_v$

$$\sigma_b = \frac{(b_1 - 0.5l_c - 0.5t) * (0.5t * (R_1)_v)}{\left(\frac{w * t^3}{12}\right)} = 1.5056 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Total stress,

$$\sigma = \sigma_b + \sigma_c = 1.645 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Allowable stress,

$$\sigma_c = \frac{38.73}{2} = 19.36 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Diameter of shaft under flywheel,

$$(M_b)_v = (R_E)_v * c_2 = 159584.080 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

$$(M_b)_H = (R_E)_v * c_2 = 306439.576 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

$$(M_b) = \sqrt{(M_b)_v^2 + (M_b)_H^2} = 345502.955 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Diameter of shaft,

$$d_s = 107.55 \text{ mm}$$

Case-II: On the basis of maximum torsional moment.

TABLE III

Reaction forces at different locations of crankshaft

Point	Description	Reaction(kg)		Moment(kg-mm)	
		Horiz.	Vert.	Horiz.	Vert.
A	Bearing1	-588.8	-118.4	0	0
B	HP Crank	-1740	-1570	-46775.1	13264.8
C	LP Crank	3460	-3120.9	124904.7	173986.1
D	HP Crank	-1740	-1570	-152562	-41364.1
E	Bearing2	352.9	353.3	214937.5	56769.3
F	Flywheel	961.6	254.0	0	0

Bending moment is highest at point D. So resultant bending moment,

$$M_d = \sqrt{(M_{DH})^2 + (M_{DV})^2} = 219.191 * 10^3 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Torsional moment at D is given by,

$$M_t = F_t * r = 130509 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

$$(M_{te}) = \sqrt{(M_d * K_b)^2 + (M_t * K_t)^2} = 353738.339 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Diameter of shaft under shear strength,

$$\tau = \frac{\Pi}{16 * d_c^3} M_{te}$$

$$d_c = 43.01 \text{ mm}$$

Diameter of shaft under bending strength,

$$M_{be} = \frac{1}{2} [M_b * K_b + M_{te}] = 341262.169 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

$$d_c = \sqrt[3]{\frac{32 * M_{be}}{\pi * \sigma_b}} = 45.15 \text{ mm}$$

Design of crankpin,

$$(M_{te}) = \sqrt{(M_b * K_b)^2 + (M_t * K_t)^2} = 110485.7 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Diameter on the basis of shear strength,

$$d_c = \frac{16}{\pi * \tau} M_{te} = 49.839 \text{ mm}$$

Diameter on the bending strength,

$$M_{be} = \frac{1}{2} [M_b * K_b + M_{te}] = 105687.1 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

$$d_c = \sqrt[3]{\frac{32 * M_{be}}{\pi * \sigma_b}} = 30.5 \text{ mm}$$

Design of web:

Bending moment due to radial component,

$$(M_b)_r = (R_E)_v * [b_2 - 0.5l_c - 0.5t] = 40097.3 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Bending stress due to radial component,

$$(\sigma_b)_r = \frac{(M_b)_r}{\frac{1}{6} * w * t^2} = 2.823 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Bending moment due to tangential component,

$$(M_b)_t = P_t * \left(r - \frac{d_{s1}}{2}\right) = 44342.5076 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Bending stress due to tangential component,

$$(\sigma_b)_t = \frac{(M_b)_t}{\frac{1}{6} * w^2 * t} = 1.92 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Direct compressive stress due to radial component,

$$(\sigma_c)_d = \frac{P_r}{2 * w * t} = 0.3506 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Maximum compressive stress,

$$\sigma_c = (\sigma_b)_t + (\sigma_b)_r + (\sigma_c)_d = 5.0936 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Torsional moment

$$(M_t) = (R_2)_h \left[b_2 - \frac{l_c}{2} \right] = 208.053 * 10^3 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

$$(M_b)_t = \frac{4.5 M_t}{w * t^2} = 11.0068 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Maximum compressive stress

$$(M_b)_t = \frac{\sigma_c}{2} + \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{(\sigma_c)^2 + 4\tau^2} = 12.82 \text{ Kg} / \text{mm}^2$$

Diameter of shaft under flywheel,

$$(M_b) = (R_E * c) = 111628.349 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

$$(M_t) = (P_t * r) = 259500 \text{ Kg} - \text{mm}$$

Diameter on the basis of shear strength,

$$(d_c)^3 = \frac{16}{\pi * \tau} \sqrt{M_b^2 + M_t^2} = 39.89 \text{ mm}$$

Diameter on the basis of bending strength,

$$(d_c)^3 = \frac{32 * M_E}{\pi * \sigma_b} = 37.60 \text{ mm}$$

3. ANALYSIS:

3.1 STATIC ANALYSIS OF CRANKSHAFT:

Figure 3.3: Total Deformation of Crankshaft

3.2 TRANSIENT ANALYSIS OF CRANKSHAFT

Figure 3.4: Boundary condition for Transient analysis of Crankshaft

Figure 3.5: Equivalent von-mises stress for Crankshaft in Transient

Figure 3.6: Total Deformation of Crankshaft in Transient

Figure 3.2: Equivalent von-mises stress for Crankshaft

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

From FEA static analysis maximum stress on crankshaft is 67.67 MPa and in transient analysis it is 82.05 MPa. Allowable value of stress for crankshaft is 90 MPa. The maximum deformation obtained in static analysis is

0.27 mm and in transient analysis 0.09mm, which is very small. Thus crankshaft design is safe.

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REFERENCES:

- 1) N. Levecque , J. Mahfoud , D. Violette, G. Ferraris , R. Dufour “*Vibration reduction of a single cylinder reciprocating compressor based on multi-stage balancing*”, University of de lyon, France, October 2010.
- 2) J.A. Becerra , F.J. Jimenez, M. Torres, D.T. Sanchez, E. Carvajal, “*Failure analysis of reciprocating compressor*

crankshafts”, High School of Engineering, University of Seville, Spain, December 2010

- 3) Mr. Mathapati N. C., Dr. Dhamejani C. L. “*FEA of a crankshaft in crank-pin web fillet region for improving fatigue life*”, International journal of innovations in engineering research and technology, Volume 2, Issue 6 June.-2015.
- 4) Bin-yan YU, Xiao-ling YU, Quan-ke FENG, “*Simple Modeling and Modal Analysis of Reciprocating Compressor Crankshaft System*”, School of Energy and Power, Xi’an Jiao tong University, China 2010.
- 5) Dr. C. M. Ramesha, Abhijith K G, Abhinav Singh, Abhishek Raj, “*Modal Analysis and Harmonic Response Analysis of a Crankshaft*”, International Journal of Emerging Technology and Advanced Engineering Volume 5, Issue 6, June 2015.

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